

Sample Name: dNTPs ATP mix 40uM

```

=====
Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                      Seq. Line :    5
Sample Operator : SYSTEM
Acq. Instrument : HPLC-UV-FC                 Location  :    5
Injection Date  : 12/10/2020 2:06:28 PM      Inj       :    1
                                           Inj Volume: 50.000 µl
Method         : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2020-12-10
                12-20-56\dNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed   : 12/10/2020 10:10:22 AM by SYSTEM
=====
    
```


Fraction Information

No Fractions found.

Area Percent Report

```

Sorted By      :      Signal
Multiplier     :      1.0000
Dilution       :      1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs
    
```

Signal 1: VWD1 A, Wavelength=254 nm

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	8.177	BB	0.1327	21.34086	2.50900	0.1750
2	10.460	BV R	0.2133	1398.86633	104.24557	11.4714
3	10.807	VB E	0.1656	53.87053	4.81051	0.4418
4	12.933	BV R	0.1923	2919.24536	238.42551	23.9393
5	13.339	VB E	0.2196	26.73439	1.71590	0.2192
6	14.723	BB	0.2060	1521.02710	114.42365	12.4732

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Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
7	16.167	BB	0.2058	3251.72485	242.70683	26.6658
8	18.314	BB	0.2153	3001.56714	214.96402	24.6144

Totals : 1.21944e4 923.80098

```
=====
*** End of Report ***
```